

InvenioRDM and maDMPs integration

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The introduction and implementation of maDMPs are crucial to ensure efficient research data management from planning to archiving the data. It is important to include various organisational units of an institution in the development process to ensure the interoperability with existing systems. One of the first integrations that we aim as a team is the information exchange between maDMPs and the institutional repository, i.e., InvenioRDM.

The goal of this hackathon is to establish a mapping between data models of maDMPs and InvenioRDM, i.e., specifying the fields from maDMPs that can be used in InvenioRDM and vice-versa

[The Machine-actionable Data Management planning](#)

[application \(DMap\)](#)

[InvenioRDM app](#)

Results

We have achieved the establishment of mappings between data models of maDMPs and invenioRDM as well as a first integration between a prototypical implementation of maDMPs and a testing instance of InvenioRDM.

We also implemented a prototype submission button to call the InvenioRDM API and push the metadata. After the submission the publication becomes available at the invenioRDM repository with the resource type 'Publication / Data management plan'. See results [Slides](#)

Future work

We will work on providing a module for invenioRDM that will handle the maDMPs import/export and mapping of data models.